

BIOACTIVE SURFACE MODIFICATION IN THE IMPLANT.UZ DENTAL IMPLANT SYSTEM: EVIDENCE FROM A CLINICAL CASE

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ANNOTATION

The presented clinical case demonstrates a standard approach to the treatment of edentulism by implantation with implants with a bioactive coating of the “Implant.Uz” system.

Key words: implantation, Implant.Uz, bioactive coating.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of tooth loss currently causes a certain amount of stress for patients. According to modern literature, many positive results of dental implantation are given.

Researchers refer to the phenomenon of osseointegration as the process by which an implant becomes integrated into the body through a strong bond between bone tissue and the implant. This strong connection results in the implant functioning reliably and stably over a long period. The mechanisms that initiate osseointegration begin immediately after implant placement. This process begins by wetting the surface of the biomaterial with a layer of physically adsorbed water, which occurs in a fraction of a second. The next step involves bringing the surface of the implant into contact with large molecules in the body, and this can take anywhere from a few seconds to several hours. It is then that the process of attaching proteins to the surface and giving them a certain shape occurs. It's worth noting that smaller proteins tend to attach faster than larger ones. However, over time, proteins with weaker affinity for the implant surface are replaced by more adhesive ones. Surface charge plays a large role in the adhesion of proteins because they are composed of amino acids with different acid-base sites. The third stage, which lasts from several minutes to several days, is when active interaction of the implant surface with cells begins. Proteins also play a significant role in this process. The proteins albumin, fibronectin and vitronectin play important roles in controlling how cells stick together. Fibrinogen affects the process of blood cell adhesion, and immunoglobulin is responsible for the body's reaction to foreign objects, such as an implant, entering it. In addition, collagen is closely associated with connective tissue cells. The process of osseointegration can be broken down into the most important stage, which is the adhesion and movement of bone-forming cells to the implant surface. Once sufficient adhesion is achieved, cell proliferation and differentiation occurs, leading to the secretion of extracellular matrix and various associated markers. The result is an immature or coarsely fibrous bone structure. Following this, tissue mineralization occurs. Over several weeks, the collagen matrix expands until the osteoblasts finally separate from each other and are essentially enclosed in an extracellular matrix. At this stage, they lose the ability to reproduce and become star-shaped osteocytes with branching processes. Scientists emphasize that after the formation of immature bone tissue, restructuring due to osteocyte cells has a profound effect on osseointegration. All of these processes are directly proportional to the structure of dental implants. A clinical example shows the installation of dental implants “Implant.Uz” with a bioactive coating.

Materials and methods of research.

Our work provides a clinical example on implants with a bioactive coating of the “Implant.Uz” system.

Due to the presence of a bioactive chitosan coating, this implant has a higher ability to attach to bone tissue. Also, the process of osseointegration is increased due to the presence of microrelief.

Clinical example.

A 56-year-old patient came to the clinic department of the Tashkent State Dental Institute with a complaint of dental defects. A clinical and radiological study was carried out, during which it was decided to install implants in place of the missing teeth.

Fig.1. Picture before treatment

The installation of dental implants was carried out according to the generally accepted protocol (Fig. 1-6). The operation was performed under local anesthesia; an incision was made and the flap was folded back with further formation of a bed for the implant. In cases of lack of bone tissue, the patient underwent bone grafting using the “Q-Oss” material (South Korea), the flap was sutured and, if necessary, patients were prescribed anti-inflammatory drugs, and lessons were given on oral hygiene. During the postoperative period, we monitored the patients until the sutures were removed on the 12th day.

Three months after the operation, a control radiography was performed (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Photo after treatment

When installing the gum formers, we were convinced of the consistency of the implants (Fig. 3-4).

Figure 3–4. Installed gum formers.

2 weeks after the installation of the gum formers, impressions were taken to make permanent ceramic structures (Fig. 5-6).

Fig 5. Installed abutments.

Figure 5. Installed zirconium dioxide crowns.

Conclusion:

This clinical case demonstrates the effectiveness of using the Implant.Uz implantation system. The presented system can be used to replace single and multiple dental defects.

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